

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF "TURKESTAN COLLECTION" IN STUDYING THE HISTORY OF FERGHANA VALLEY

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada "Turkiston to'plami" bibliografik asarining yaratilish tarixi, ushbu asarning Markaziy Osiyo tarixi o'rganishdagi o'rni va ahamiyati, Markaziy Osiyoning Chor Rossiyasi hukmronligi davridagi ijtimoiy hamda iqtisodiy hayoti bilan bog'liq masalalar yuzasidan qisqacha ma'lumotlar o'rin olgan.

Annotation: This article contains brief information about the history of the creation of the bibliographic work "Turkistan Collection", the place and importance of this work in the study of the history of Central Asia, and issues related to the social and economic life of Central Asia during the rule of Tsarist Russia.

Аннотация: В данной статье содержится краткая информация об истории создания библиографического труда «Туркестанский сборник», месте и значении этого труда в изучении истории Средней Азии, а также вопросах, связанных с общественно-экономической жизнью Средней Азии в период правления царской России.

Kalit so'zlar: Turkistonto'plami, ChorRossiyasi, FonKaufman, MarkaziyOsiyo, madaniyat, tarix, ilm-fan,TurkistonXalqkutubxonasi, VM.Mejov, K. Betger.

Keywords: Turkestan Collection, Czar Russia, Von Kaufman, Central Asia, culture, history, science, Turkestan Public Library, VM. Mezhov, K. Betger.

Ключевые слова: Туркестанский сборник, царская Россия, фон Кауфман, Средняя Азия, культура, история, наука, Туркестанская публичная библиотека, В. М. Межов, К. Бетгер.

Introdition. In the context of the development of the new Uzbekistan and in the process of implementing fundamental reforms, national revival, spiritual renewal, national identity and uniqueness have been fully understood, have a free democratic way of thinking and are united by the power of a strong national idea. the role of the science of history in solving the tasks of educating members of the society is seriously increasing.

of the head of our state, Sh.M. Mirziyo, devoted to the problems of forming the idea of national independence, the mobilization of the spiritual potential of the science of history, a broad program of actions in the field of restoration of historical truth, the chosen path of independence and development, and reaching the intended goals a solid scientific basis of achievement was determined.They have a communitythe need to deeply study the real laws of development, to analyze the periods of growth and crisis in national history from a new methodological point of view, to identify the factors related to the destructive influence of the Tsarist and Soviet colonial-imperial systems, to change the previous ideological patterns and old ways of thinking It is noted that it is necessary to determine the ways to end the repetition

of the manifestations, to strengthen the influence of the science of history in the achievement of spiritual and moral improvement of the society.

Based on these important social tasks, re-evaluation of the sad pages of our country's history related to the difficult colonial past from today's point of view is of particular importance. The high social need to refer to them and its scientific importance are first determined by the fact that the history of colonialism (the Soviet era was also a component of this history) was extremely falsified and distorted as a result of the tsar's rule and the dictatorial policy carried out during the years of Soviet power. . For many years, our social consciousness has been informed about the extraordinary "civilizing task" of the tsarist Russia and the communist regime in Central Asia, and the fact that the "backward" peoples of the country have allegedly achieved "great success" as a result of the state administration of the center. the myth about was vigorously propagated. However, it did not say anything about the barbaric nature of the economic policy implemented by the tsarist government and the Soviet government, and the fact that the tsarist authoritarian regime was a continuation of the imperial colonial tradition was forcefully shown. In those years, the country's natural raw material resources were transported non-stop, thousands of years of national and cultural wealth of the Uzbek people were looted, and the policy of moral oppression was implemented.

Taking into account the stated circumstances, it is necessary to reasonably reject the statements that falsify the truth of history, it is time to carry out fundamental research aimed at scientifically clearly revealing the fact that the Uzbek people lived under colonial oppression for more than 130 years, based on sufficient documentary materials. is one of the urgent requirements.

After the conquest of the territory of Central Asia by Tsarist Russia, the region was discriminated both economically and socially. All aspects of economic life began to serve the interests of the empire. The standard of living of the population has become relatively favorable, and as a result, several popular protests have been carried out. Most of the information about this and similar events has been recorded in the "Turkestan Collection".

Literature analysis and methodology.After the conquest of the territory of Central Asia by Tsarist Russia, the region was discriminated both economically and socially. All aspects of economic life began to serve the interests of the empire. The standard of living of the population has become relatively favorable, and as a result, several popular protests have been carried out. Most of the information about this and similar events has been recorded in the "Turkestan Collection".

Since the independence of our country, great researches have been carried out in the field of history, as well as in many fields. Falsified historical information was eliminated on the basis of the principle of objectivity, and great advances were made in science. In particular, on the basis of the materials of the "Turkestan Collection" recorded during the time of Tsarist Russia, studies of the basic content of the policy implemented during the colonial period were carried out. Many of our historical scientists gave new scientific conclusions about the history of Tsarist Russia through this bibliographic work and supported their dissertation work.

After the occupation of the territory of Central Asia by Tsarist Russia, as a result of the policies carried out in the country, its social, economic, political, cultural and social life was greatly damaged. We can also see that the persons who worked in the leadership of Tsarist Russia did not hide their dissatisfaction with some aspects of Turkestan administration in the

press of that time. "Turkestan" written on the basis of materials collected during 1867-1917 In sbornik " ("Turkistan Collection") you can find many examples of this. In this collection, we can find materials written on the basis of facts, but not in detail, about political processes, economic life, ethnoculture, economic and social processes of Turkestan during the Russian Empire.

As a result of the wrong policy of the Tsarist Russian authorities in the Turkestan region, the living standards of the inhabitants of the country decreased. The people of the country suffered a lot due to the leadership and administrative command and one-sided policy in the management process.

After the conquest of Central Asia by the Russian Empire, Russian researchers focused on studying the ethno-social characteristics of the Ferghana Valley and managed to collect scientific data. A wealth of information can be obtained regarding the ethnography of the valley peoples, although their research is focused on their primary interests. In this place, it is possible to note the scientific investigations carried out by H. Potanin, A. Middendorf, VV Velyaminov-Zernov, A. Shishov, APXoroshkin, V. Firsov, NFSitnyakovskiy, AIBryanov, A. Divayev, A. Kasatkin, AEKushakevich, PEKuznetsov. In their research, information related to the daily life and customs of the people of the Fergana Valley, the traditions of the national economy, especially farming, animal husbandry, and handicrafts are provided. Some authors have also provided information about traditional farms. Among the articles in the "Turkestan Collection" there are some articles devoted to the horse-breeding of the valley population, the authors of which are not known. [4:462]

the "Turkestan collection" the attention to the study of economic traditions and the ethnoculture of the Ferghana Valley, their regional and general characteristics, especially intensified in the years of independence, historical, archaeological, a number of works were carried out in terms of local history and ethnology. In particular, MRJabborov, AAshirov, USAbdullayev, G. Valikhonova conducted research using the materials of the "Turkistan Collection" within the framework of their topics.

Results. In the second half of the 19th century, the main objects of the invasion policy of the Russian Empire were the Bukhara Emirate, Kokand and Khiva Khanates in Central Asia. One by one, Russia, which took advantage of their independence, lack of mutual cooperation, and, on the contrary, their growing internal struggle for supremacy in the region, subjugated them one by one. This act of invasion of Tsarism was not limited to conquering a foreign territory and turning it into a colony, but it was also aimed at damaging the culture and spiritual foundations of the local population. caused him to resist with the fact that its echoes were felt even in our days - at the end of the 20th century. As a proof of our point, it is enough to highlight the sharp and prolonged conflict between the leadership and the society. The real historical process of the middle of the 19th century coincides with the beginning of the colonial period and the conquest of the region by Russian troops. [11:93] _ _

The escalation of events in the second half of the 19th century was also played by an international factor - the fierce competition between Russia and England for influence in Central Asia.

For example, in 1858, three expeditions were organized at once: a "scientific" expedition led by the orientalist NV Khanikov to Iran and the oasis of Herat; The trade expedition led by Ch. Valikhonov was sent to Kashkar (South-Eastern Turkestan) and Kokan Khanate. This

expedition was led by Colonel NPIgnatyev, the Russian military agent in London, a supporter of the policy of attacking Central Asia.

Representatives of Russian trade and industry circles were introduced. For example, more than 190 people accompanied the diplomatic mission of NPIgnat y ev. Even the Arol flotilla under the command of AIButakov was given at his disposal.

The "advisory councils" in St. Petersburg, with the participation of the governors-general of Orenburg and Western Siberia, AA Katenin and Gasford, who were close neighbors of the Central Asian khanates, ranged from scouting places in Central Asia to preparing for the occupation of certain settlements. began to draw up specific plans of actions. The action of Venyukov's reconnaissance detachments in the Kokan lands in the Chu River basin region ended with the capture of Tokmok and Pishpek in the spring and summer of 1859, and the Kokan fortresses in 1860 and 1862. On August 1, 1863, the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the Ministry of War agreed on "General comments on future actions in Central Asia". On December 20, 1863, a tsar's decree was announced on the unification of the Orenburg and Siberian military-strategic road. This signaled the end of the stage of reconnaissance expeditions and scattered military campaigns, and the beginning of a large-scale military campaign against the Central Asian states. [10:42] _ _

Important aspects of the history of the colonial period of the Russian Empire, including the development trends of industry, agriculture and cultural life here, the history of some cities, changes in the structure of the population of the valley, the struggle for national liberation against the tyranny of the colonialists in the region, and other issues were researched based on historical sources. As a result, there was an opportunity to cover the history of Ferghana during the Russian colonial period in an objective and impartial way. In this period, the problem we have chosen is studied on a new conceptual and methodological basis, and it is known in this regard progress has been made.

Among the information gathered on 457 roofs of the "Turkestan collection", such information can be found in the article written on the issue of establishing a Russian city in the city of Ko'kan.

" Before the acquisition of Kokan by the Russians, there were many sarts here, who organized their own special, closed colonies, had their own caravansary, paid taxes , and used polite sarts ruthlessly; now, as a result of the persecution of the usurious administration, their number has significantly decreased. Kazan and Ufa Tatars sell food products and red goods, serve as translators and servants, grow gardens, conclude contracts; in general, their employment is very diverse. The number of Afghans engaged in trade is very small, some of them you will meet on the streets, and finally those who speak Russian - this is a small but dominant segment of the population, mainly officials, soldiers and merchants. " Razpochint " (comers) are very few; they do not gravitate toward a steady state and are generally more variable than constant content. I mentioned above that due to its excellent trade position, Kokan developed quickly and became one of the main markets of Central Asia. [8:123]

This is how the Russian officer describes the ways of attacking the customs and traditions of the local population after the conquest of the Kokan Khanate. " Among the Kokan population of Russia, in my opinion, this is a great way to communicate with the natives: and they learn to leave, and we are in constant contact with them and deliberately forget to look at them, because they show us animals like faces under slavery. compare with etc. to hit as desired; we treat them as equal citizens of our great motherland, they have already learned and lived by the justice of

Russian laws.

Speaking from experience, I have been living in Kokon for 10 years, and I have never ignored any manifestation of bigotry by local residents; on the contrary, I always found them helpful, humble, polite, even a little shy. The mullah's fanatics have lost all meaning and can no longer influence the people with their fiery voices.

People want only peace and quiet under the general protection of the law. It is impossible to repeat the holy "ghazavot", that is, the fight against the insane. I finished; we wish the young Russian Kokan to develop as fast as the old Asian one and walk side by side for success. I wish industry, trade and general prosperity . [11:93]

The authors of some articles from the "Turkestan Collection" noted that Ferghana has a long history of farming traditions. In particular, the following meaning was written down by Zhang Zian of Dovan (Chinese ambassador who visited the state of Fergana) V. Yuferov, author of the essay "Fergana region sartlar hojaligi" ("Hozyaystvo sartov Ferganskoy oblasti") in the 2nd century BC gives the information: "The people of Dovan grow rice and wheat and lead a sedentary life. They also eat musallas made from grapes . " [9:526] In his article "Historical Essay" ("Historical Essay"), DDSemyon recalls that in the 7th century AD, the Chinese traveler Hsuen-Sang (more precisely, Xuan Xiang) crossed to India through the Ferghana Valley .

Information about the Islamic traditions of water use in the Ferghana Valley and the procedures established during the tsarist government were also recorded by some authors in the collection.

Discussion. Before the Russian invasion, the industry in the Ferghana Valley had a handicraft character. Work tools, household goods, shoes, clothes and other products used in the daily life of the population were produced in small craft enterprises. However, in the middle of the 19th century, small factories of military importance and small textile factories appeared in the Kokan Khanate. According to the article written by A.Kun from the "Turkestan Collection", an Afghan engineer educated in India will build a weapons factory in the khanate. [10:44-45]

After the conquest of Tsarist Russia, factories and factories were built in Turkestan, including the Fergana region, in order to effectively use the country's natural resources and to process the agricultural products grown on the spot. Since cotton growing is the leading branch of agriculture in the region, the first industries such as cotton ginning, oil-oil, and soap making were created.

ginning factory was built and put into operation by the Kamensky brothers in the city of Ko'kan . 60,000 rubles were spent on the construction of the plant. The enterprise has 6 fiber separating machines, 2 parchers and 3 pressing devices . [2:193]

According to the information provided in the "Turkiston Collection" collection, the second cotton ginning factory in the Fergana region was built and put into operation in 1884 by the merchant Silakhtin in the city of Ko'kan. Lakhtin was the first to wrap the cotton in paperset off. This method was much cheaper than local methods. Cotton processed at the Lakhtin enterprise is considered to be of the highest quality, and each bushel of cotton is sold at 75 kopecks on the Moscow market.

Summary. A number of materials from the collection provide noteworthy information about the cultural life of the Fergana Valley. In particular, information about old schools and madrasahs, Russian-system schools, materials about the creation and development of health

care centers in the region are noteworthy. However, due to the negative attitude of the Russian authorities to modern schools, the activities of these schools are hardly covered in the program. However, modern schools played an important role in the development of national education.

The trade relations of Fergana region with the Russian Empire and foreign countries are well covered in the pages of "Turkestan Collection". Sources show that as a result of the construction of railways, Fergana was drawn into the framework of the All-Russian and world market.

One issue that is not adequately reflected in the collection is the popular movement in the Fergana Valley against the colonial policies of the Russian Empire. The research of this issue showed that only the uprising of 1873-1876, the Andijan uprising of 1898 and the activities of Kurbanjon dodkhoh were partially covered in the pages of the collection. The articles devoted to these issues are very shallow in terms of content and do not reveal the true nature of the events. Thus, the "Turkistan Collection" is the economic, social, political and cultural life of the Fergana Valley in the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. is an important historical source that provides a lot of interesting information about Wide and critical use of the information in the collection is of great importance in researching the history of the Turkestan region and the Fergana Valley on a deep scientific basis during this period. Some materials in the "Turkestan Collection" provide an opportunity to supplement and clarify information in other written historical sources. A series of data in the collection is distinguished by its originality and uniqueness. Therefore, in researching the history of the Fergana Valley during the period of the Russian Empire's colonization, it is appropriate to widely use the materials included in the "Turkestan Collection" collection along with other sources.

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